

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPT OF "LEARNERS' ACTIVITY" IN THE TRAINING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The article focuses on the diversity of opinions regarding the interpretation of the concepts of "training" and "training process", referring to the research conducted on scientific sources, establishment of the concept of "educational activity of students" in educational psychology, formation of new pedagogical thinking, achievement of success in the field of activity concept, the possibility of approaching the concepts of "training", "training process", "educational activity of students" from a new point of view is emphasized, determining the emergence of the concept of "teaching activity" in pedagogical psychology and it is stated that the model of educational activity reflects its emergence and development (the concept of "educational activity").

Based on the concept of educational activity, the interpretation of the concept of "student activity" in the learning process is given by selecting the components of the structure of educational activity as a point of view.

Keywords: system; subsystem; pedagogical process; training; training process; educational activity; structure of educational activity; teaching tasks; teaching situation; teaching operations; control; evaluation.

Relevance of the research topic. The lack of unanimity of opinion regarding the interpretation of the concepts of "training" and "training process", the emergence of the concept of "teaching activity" in pedagogical psychology, the establishment of theoretical considerations about the constituent parts of the structure of teaching activity based on the concept of teaching activity, the concept of "student activity" in the training process has created conditions for its interpretation.

Which: 1) the existence of such an interpretation has a significant impact on the activities of educators (and students) in the direction of the formation of the performance of educational operations, self-control and self-evaluation skills of students;

2) the main components of the educational implementation process can benefit from the success of psychology in solving the mentioned issue (building skills);

3) in addition to this, the development of the teaching methodology on the subject of interpretation, which we consider important to be developed, is served. Despite what has been said, we claim the relevance of the research on the topic "Interpretation of the concept of activity of students in the training process".

Interpretation of generalizations on research materials of the collection. It is clear from the research conducted on scientific sources that there was a diversity of opinions regarding the interpretation of the concepts of "training" and "training process" and the mentioned feature remains in the views of our contemporaries.

From the works of ancient and medieval thinkers, we can conclude that they (the thinkers who worked in that time period) mainly meant the concept of "teaching" in exchange for the concepts of "training" and "training process". At the beginning of the 20th century, the concepts of "teaching" and "learning" that

make up this process were included in the concept of "training".

As arguments confirming the existence of diversity of opinion regarding the concepts of "training", "training process", "teaching", "learning", the opinions of the thinkers listed below can be an example. Professors A.Kh. Pashayev and FARustamov emphasize in their comments on these concepts that when they say "teaching" they mean the activities of teachers to organize the assimilation of lesson material. Learning is understood as the activity of learners to master the material. The managerial activity of the teacher to shape the cognitive activity of the learners, the joint activity of the teacher and the learners is also reflected in the concept of training. The following signs are typical for training in the modern sense: 1) two-sided character; 2) joint activity of teachers and students; 3) guidance by the teacher; 4) to organize and manage the education, development and formation of students in accordance with the plan; 5) completeness and unity; 6) compliance with the regularities of age development of students. [10; 132]. BAAhmedov, AQRzayev's interesting comments are in such a text: "training under the guidance of U (the teacher is meant) with the application of V (the word, visuality, methods, educational material, in general, what is at the disposal of the teacher) of S (referring to secondary school students) is the process of understanding life, acquiring knowledge, skills and habits". They succinctly presented their ideas in this regard as follows: "Education is the process of the learner's understanding of life with the help of the teacher's guidance and appropriate tools" [2;114].

According to Professor N.M.Kazimov, training is one of the most complex concepts of pedagogy. In this concept, the content, stages, tasks, activity characteristics of the teacher and the learner meet organically and

condition each other. Training is the process of acquiring knowledge, skills and habits, education and development of learners under the guidance of the teacher. In this sense, training is inseparable from education; it can be understood as the process of implementation of education [7; 81]. Academician MM Mehdi-zadeh said, "The educational process is a joint activity of the teacher and the learner with a certain structure, which uses the components of the system of knowledge, skills and habits, forms, types and methods of training, didactic, visual and technical aids to improve the education, upbringing and development of students (students) is aimed at ensuring", - considers his opinion more acceptable [9; 52]. FN Ibrahimov and RL Huseynzade gave the following definition to the training process: "the training process in general education schools under the guidance of the teacher is a pedagogical process that directs the students to provide their knowledge, skills and habits more effectively in order to accelerate their preparation for life, where the students are mentally, morally, psychologically developed according to their capabilities and the acts of involvement in practical activity are legally carried out in unity" [6; 402].

It is emphasized in one of the Russian-language scientific sources: "the educational process consists of the set of such consistent activities of the teacher and the students led by him that enables schoolchildren to consciously and firmly master the system of knowledge, skills and habits, and as a result, to develop their cognitive powers, to make them mentally and arming with the culture of physical labor, aimed at forming the foundations of students' outlook and behavior" [13; 176]. In the other, "The learning process is the legal replacement of the acts of his interaction with the teacher in order for the learner to master a certain part of the social experience, during which the activities of both the teacher and the student change, the student acquires new qualities. [6; 398].

Here we need to focus on one aspect. Most pedagogues highlight the leadership function of educators as the main feature in the training process. In our opinion, during the process of "sharing" of human experience in the educational space that is being adequately formed to the convocations of the IV industrial revolution (implementation of the training process, which is considered the form of action (path) of this process), the condition that the parties must have natural intelligence can be put into the background. can transform the necessary part of it into its own personality with artificial intelligence.

Without deviating from the goal of our research, finally, we consider what has been presented sufficient to confirm our opinion on the existence of diversity of opinions regarding the scientific interpretation of the concepts of "training", "training process", and we consider it necessary to generalize with the opinions of the outstanding psychologist A.A. Alizadeh. [1 ;150]. Prof. A. A. Alizade writes that training is one of the main concepts of pedagogy. From the first day of its pedagogy, he used this concept widely and investigated the psychological problems of training in various direc-

tions. In educational psychology, the concept of "educational activity of the student" was formed and established. The establishment of new pedagogical thinking, on the other hand, the successes achieved in the field of the activity concept gave the opportunity to approach these issues from a new aspect, and the concept of "teaching activity" was born in pedagogical psychology.

Professor A.A. Alizade specifically emphasizes that the teaching activity is multifaceted. Although training is an important characteristic of educational activity, it does not cover all its aspects. Training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits. However, acquisition and educational activity are essentially different events. Appropriation is an integral part not only of the learning process, but of every activity (play or work). Teaching activity is a type of activity, a unique form of social activity of the personality. [there]

According to our opinion, the "system-structure" approach is a reliable research method in the spiritual analysis of reality, in clarifying its essence, in making concepts (categorical apparatus) into a system, in interpreting the dialectic between concepts (in fact, it is a dialectical scientific research method). We claim that the object of pedagogy (in educational institutions, the object in question is the pedagogical process) is a system that includes education, training, development as parts of a unit, which the science of pedagogy should reveal the laws and principles that determine the perfection of that system (in other words, to develop an adequate theory directed). We consider it logical to separate the subsystems of this system by approaching the aspects of understanding reality and personality formation (based on this paradigm, the pedagogical process should be accepted as a "big system"-containing system, and the teaching process and educational process should be accepted as a "small system"-containing system, the interpretation of the mentioned concepts and we consider them useful in terms of organizing and managing adequate real processes, in other words, we consider it an acceptable option to be based on the idea of SaShapronsky) [4; 44 and 104-107]

When we approach the learning process as a subsystem (in relation to the learning process), its two main organizing components or elements are immediately noticeable without going into details: the teacher and the learner. Therefore, training tasks are carried out during the joint activity of two parties - in the conditions of unity of teaching and learning processes. Performance of training tasks at a high level requires a system of activities that conditions each other from the teacher and students. The training activity of the students is the activity directed towards the realization of the goal of the training process. It has both an objective and a subjective side. Let us specially emphasize that if the student's activity is not aimed at the implementation of his duties in the training process, it cannot be considered as training activity. Therefore, the objective side of the training activity is related to its orientation to the goals set before the training, without the learner being dependent on himself. The subjective aspect of the training activity is characterized and determined by

the dominant motives of this activity. The dominant motives of the training activity may or may not be educational-cognitive motives. It is desirable that the motives of the activity are educational-cognitive motives. The teacher's pedagogical influence should be aimed at creating this situation. In this case, if the objective and subjective sides of the training activity do not coincide, then the motives that dominate the motivation of the training activity are not educational-cognitive motives.

The activity of students in the training process is integral, it is a condition that it is divided into teaching-cognition and control-evaluation. This is important for a better analysis of training activities. It should be emphasized that in the training process, the genetic-structure and functional-structure of the activities of the learner and the educator are distinguished and justifications are presented about their compatibility (interdependence). According to M.L.Fridman, any activity, including training activity, consists of the following elements: demand-motive-goal-task-working conditions-operation. All of them are carried out under certain internal and external conditions regarding the student's activity. They should be included in the structure of the activity. It is possible to describe the structure of any activity with the same scheme. L.M.Fridman shows that the model of training activity reflects its creation and development. [16; 178-179]

The concept of educational activity formed by D.V.Elkonin, V.V.Davidov and others distinguishes the following components in the structure of educational activity: 1) educational situation (or tasks); 2) educational operations; 3) control; 4) price. [1; 150]. We appreciate the division of the structure of the educational activity into parts that are considered relatively independent in the presented content, and when formulating our conclusions, we found it necessary to give priority to the said presentation, and we accepted its logic.

As it is known, the author of one of the concepts related to the structure of training is the outstanding psychologist A.N.Leontyev. He distinguished the understanding of a class of concrete objects, their properties, as well as generalized cognitive processes made it. He showed that the first consists of knowledge, skills and habits and the possibility of acquiring them in the learning process. The second ones are abilities. And mastering them occurs in the process of developing understanding. [4;237]

The views of the Azerbaijani psychologist M. A. Hamzayev regarding the structure of training are also interesting. He shows that it is possible to include the following components in the structure of training: cognitive requirements, training motives, training goals, tasks, teaching tasks.

Teaching jobs are different. Inciting (executive), programmatic, active-operational, control-regulatory (evaluative, checking, corrective) works can be attributed to this [3;131].

It should be noted that these considerations, directly or indirectly related to the structure of training, are in fact, in a certain sense, complementary to each other. The facts we obtained on the basis of psychological research allow us to justify such a well-known fact

that the satisfaction of cognitive needs is a necessary condition for the normal development of a person and also applies to his learning and training activities. When learning starts from a person's cognitive needs, it becomes the main factor that ensures his activity. From here, cognitive interests and the main motives of learning arise. Based on this, N.M.Kazimov also notes that the knowledge covered by the subjects and the process of learning this knowledge belong to the sources that create cognitive interests and needs. [7; 106]

Cognitive interests of students have different stages of development and can manifest in different forms. Such diversity is one of the reasons determining the degree of activity and independence of children in the learning process. It is possible to determine the level of development of cognitive interests in students according to their content at three levels: simple, medium and high.

The formed cognitive interest not only increases the effectiveness of the subsequent educational activities of the students in the training, but also scientifically based training can improve the cognitive interest of the students. Innovation of knowledge, problematic approach, use of science and technology innovations, knowledge for the individual and society, joining of students to creative activity, etc. are tools that help to increase cognitive interest. [4 ;233]

Cognitive demand essentially expresses students' desire for knowledge (V.S.İlyin). There is no doubt that this is due to cognitive interest. Man has a need to escape from the surrounding reality not only for the purpose of protecting himself, but also for the purpose of cognition. [15]

A lot of research has been done on the cognitive needs and interests of schoolchildren (by G.I. Shukina and others). In general, over the decades, educators and psychologists have identified the following as a result of studying cognitive demand and interest:

1. The objective basis of the development of cognitive interest in students consists of a high level of teaching, its true scientific content, and pedagogically appropriate organization of active and independent cognition.

2. The cognitive interest of learners can have a different character due to its degree of manifestation, stability and depth at different levels of development. The formless, broad and primary interest of learners forms a diverse basis for active and independent learning. The cognitive interest of learners reflects the level of understanding of events, processes and regularities by learners according to their content.

The highest level of cognitive interest development is the level of creativity, which is related to the student's interest in performing activities on deep theoretical problems, not in an easy way that is known to everyone, but in the way that the learner himself has found and planned.

3. Under the influence of cognitive interest, activity becomes easier, freer and faster, thanks to which fatigue disappears.

4. The stimulating effect of teaching on the formation of cognitive interest of students is very great. This effect comes from the content of the subject, the

activity of the students, and the relationship between the participants of the educational process. [12; 284].

In the structure of learning, learning goals and tasks also have their own place and role. It is this aspect that allows learning to be educational. In other words, learning becomes training when it takes a planned form that will fulfill certain goals and tasks, and leads to the acquisition of knowledge, skills and habits. Training is possible where human activity is guided by conscious goals to acquire certain knowledge, habits and skills. A prerequisite for the organization of training activities is the creation of conscious motives for mastering certain knowledge, skills and habits in the subject.

Training activity not only equips the learner with knowledge, skills and habits necessary for various types of socially useful activities. At the same time, it forms the ability to control one's own mental processes, to choose, organize and direct one's work and operations, habits and experience in relation to the problem to be solved.

Regardless of the level of awareness of the activity, the awareness of the goal always remains its necessary sign. In the absence of that sign, human activity, especially training activity, cannot exist.

The system of actions that make up the work is ultimately managed and regulated for the purpose of those works. The results of the actions are evaluated from the point of view of the goal and they are corrected. The purpose of the work ensures that the properties and conditions of things are a guide for its implementation, control and diagnosis.

In the training activity, the goal manifests itself as images in the brain, a dynamic model of the future result of the activity. The desired model of the future is compared with the actual result of the work, it controls and corrects the lines of the movement. Physiologists call this model of the work ahead (the program of actions) and the results that it predicts to the brain (the program of goals) "work acceptor" and "anticipatory vision" (P.K.Anokhin), "motor goal" and "the model of the required future" (N.A.Bernstein), "necessary importance" and "model of the future" (Mittelstedt, U.Ashby), "dynamic model", etc. they call Despite the fact that this diversity is the result of different assumptions about what that model is, how it is formed and how it works, the idea that future work is imagined in advance and that their expected results are reflected in the brain in a certain way is completely honest. [12; 284-285].

Educational activities, which allow to realize the goals and tasks of learning, occupy one of the main places in its structure. These types of work primarily include executive (provocative) work. A learner cannot acquire relevant knowledge, skills and habits without using those learning activities. These kinds of jobs are the jobs that direct people to action. Program-oriented work consists of oral and written work, laboratory work, etc. related to meeting the requirements of the program. consists of Active operational teaching works are works aimed at activating the mental activity of students (students), creating cognitive activity in them. Such works stimulate the intellectual development of students, and take them away from mere reproduction.

N.M.Kazimov writes that the manifestations of student activity during training can be divided into three groups: external activity, internal activity and creative activity. Intrinsic activity is perfect and more effective in learning than extrinsic activity. Pupils (educators) who have internal activity achieve success in training.

The highest form of activity is creative activity. It is typical for creative activity to explore and find ways to solve the given task, to overcome it, and sometimes to determine original means. Creative activity plays an important role in the formation of the personality of the student. [7; 106-107]

In learning, the cognitive activity of the learner cannot be separated from his independence. They complement each other. The student's independence in learning is manifested in different forms: in feeling the need for knowledge; being able to think independently; in getting out of a new situation, circumstances; creatively looking for a way to cope with a new task; eager to learn new knowledge in a radical way; in a critical approach to another's opinion on the studied issue; in being able to prove one's opinion, etc.

Manifestations of student independence in the learning process can be observed when searching for information from sources, reflecting on actual knowledge, consolidating skills, turning skills into habits, applying knowledge to practice, and using knowledge in new situations. [11;69-70]

The role of control-regulatory teaching works included in the structures of training is also great. These works are mainly of evaluative, checking and corrective nature. With their help, it is possible to manage the training activities of the students.

N.M.Kazimov specifically distinguishes the following from the features characterizing the learner's activity in training: the presence of cognitive operations in the learning process; Manifestations of cognitive operations; the role of learning motives; cognitive interests in learning; communication in learning; students' activity and independence in learning [7; 108-109].

In our opinion, N.M.Kazimov is right. In addition, it can be noted that during training, students get used to learning as well as acquiring knowledge. Learning and the ability to acquire knowledge are based on a number of cognitive operations. Special attention not only to teaching skills, but also to cognitive operations is necessary in training.

The theory of the formation of cognitive operations in the learning activity of students under the guidance of the teacher was developed by psychologists. According to the theory of the mastery of mental activity by stages (P.Y.Qalper's concept) in connection with training, the analysis of the activity is taken to the forefront, and knowledge is viewed as the creation and derivative of the activity and its mastery. According to P.Y.Qalperi, training work is a structure that has the following components: a) subject of exchange, product (resource), tools; b) the process of change, as well as reflection; c) knowledge about all the mentioned components of the activity (the basis of familiarization of the activity - FBE) [4;235]

The process of change is carried out in the form of

operations that perform three types of functions: creation of the FBE or activation of the existing FBE (introduction operation), implementation of the change itself (management operation), control and regulation (control operation).

In addition, P.Y. Qalper also showed that intellectual activity in mastering goes through the following six stages: 1) motivation stage; 2) FBE determination phase; 3) the stage of material (materialized) performance of the activity; 4) the stage of performance of the activity in oral speech (saying from above); 5) the stage of performance of the activity with the help of internal speech (saying to oneself); 6) the stage of mental performance of the activity [4; 236]

It is necessary to add to the reasoning of P.Y. Qalper that each cognitive operation can be treated as a system itself. Considering this point, N.M. Kazimov shows that the formation of any cognitive operation constitutes a system in itself, so that the learner has to perform a number of cognitive operations that replace each other while performing the educational task, and in this sense, the learning activity of the learner is both content and it manifests itself as a system of cognitive operations aimed at the performance of the teaching task in an executive manner. As with educational tasks, the cognitive operations that require their performance are also diverse.

We consider it necessary to continue with the above-mentioned considerations and thereby clarify the nature of the elements contained in the structural and functional models of teaching activity. Educational activity begins with solving educational tasks. Educational tasks can be any scientific, military, sports, etc. it is distinguished from the assignments by one important feature. Teaching tasks involve students discovering and mastering general methods (principles, laws) of solving various problems and specific issues in their educational activities. By presenting teaching tasks, the teacher introduces students to a unique teaching situation: in this situation, they learn by taking into account all specific and concrete options. they get acquainted with the content of general methods of solving their tasks, acquire relevant knowledge, skills and habits. It should be noted here that knowledge is a multifaceted meaning, and all the characteristics of the meaning of knowledge should be reflected in the information given to the student in interaction. The meaning of knowledge (information) is considered to include the following: certain facts, terminology; the methods of selection of facts; conventional signs; development trends; classification; inspection and evaluation criteria; research methods applied in the relevant field or problem; general concepts; structures and theories; the principles and laws necessary to explain and interpret events, foresee their future development; knowing the theory and structures. Let's also note that the educational tasks have many unique features, but one aspect is clear: in order to solve them, students must master the necessary educational operations.

Teaching operations are varied. Many of them are of a general nature and are used almost equally in the acquisition of various educational materials. Some ed-

ucational operations are more typical for mastering certain educational materials (mathematical, linguistic, etc.). They also distinguish teaching operations applied in special cases. Mental processes-analysis, composition, comparison, generalization, etc. According to V.V. Davidov, intellectual processes - analysis, composition, comparison, generalization, abstraction, etc. occupy a special place in the structure of educational operations. it is always carried out by applying it to the content of a particular subject and therefore always appears as the operations of a particular subject. From this point of view, the formation of educational operations is directly related to the students' acquisition of the principles of mental activity.

The training conditions and tasks included in the psychological structure of training (in the concept of DBElkonin and VVDavidov) [1; 150-151] are characterized by the fact that students are required to find general ways of working and the purpose of mastering them, as well as common ways of solving a certain type of problem. they are tasked with mastering examples and instructions. Training tasks consist of tasks related to the students' search for or discovery of scientific concepts and general modes of operation, as well as ways to remember them and apply them to the solution of typical problems. Narrat works are works aimed at summarizing the results of their training works based on the given example. Assessment works given scientific knowledge and a general way of solving the problem registers the final quality of the assimilation of

In modern educational practice, the American scientist B. Bloom's scheme (Bloom's taxonomy) about the stages of the student's cognitive activity is accepted. By the way, let's emphasize that in the history of pedagogical psychology, the 50s-70s of the last century occupy an important place as a special stage in the development of taxonomies. In these years, B. Blum, Engelhart, Furs and Kratvol (1956), J. Gilford (1967), Mak Gur (1969), D. Heinot (1977), Grønland (1970) and others. have created taxonomies in the field of cognition. [1;386]

The scheme proposed by the research is knowing, understanding, applying, analyzing (analyzing), synthesizing and evaluating cognitive activities is a description of the climbing stages. These stages unknowingly expand towards evaluation, forming a hierarchical structure. A student's mastery of skills appropriate to any stage includes skills appropriate to lower stages.

According to our opinion, the educational activity of the student (preferring the approach from the functional-structural position) can be viewed as complete, including the following stages: 1) introduction - motivation; 2) operational-cognition; 3) monitoring and evaluation.

In the introduction-motivation phase, the following training tasks can be distinguished: 1) understanding of the training-problem situation; 2) defining the main teaching tasks; 3) assessment of learning material learning opportunities.

At the operational-cognitive stage, students learn the content of the educational material, acquire knowledge (declared, operational, conditional), skills

and habits. At this time, the main teaching issue is to determine the sequence of individual tasks and solve them.

In the control-evaluation stage, students summarize what they have learned on the subject, include them in their general system of knowledge and skills, analyze the educational work they have carried out, determine whether they have fulfilled the main cognitive issue, what they have mastered, how they have achieved their goal, etc. takes the issues and makes the necessary corrections.

It is undeniable that the role of control in the formation of educational activity is significant. Whether the activity is effective or not is directly related to the level of supervision in addition to the teaching operations. In this regard, it is necessary to mention two aspects. First, the student reconciles the educational operations and their results with the purpose of his activity, identifies and eliminates his mistakes. It is necessary to always draw the attention of students to this aspect - the results of educational operations, to teach them to plan educational operations mentally, first of all, to implement them internally and to analyze their results. When Flayvel analyzes metacognitive functions, he distinguishes two aspects from the point of view of control: in the first case, the learner controls himself by organizing his attention, and in the second case, he controls the problem-solving process (as well as in other types of tasks). Both functions are of particular importance in educational activities. Secondly, when the control is effective, the student's educational activity is carried out as a manifestation of his will: he makes an effort to overcome the difficulties, he shows special activity for the realization of the goal, and the direction of his activity is determined by the mediated interest. In these conditions, control gradually turns into self-control, begins to develop effectively on the basis of reflection. Control is directly related to assessment, which is important as a unique component of educational activity [1; 153]. It should be noted that in the control process, not the final result of the educational activity, but the result of individual educational operations is examined. However, in the evaluation process, the final result of the educational activity is analyzed, and it is determined to what extent it corresponds to the purpose of the educational activity.

It should be noted that recently some authors consider educational activity as a new educational technology. Such setting of the issue is of fundamental importance and opens up new opportunities for the application of psychology to school practice. The control of educational activity as an educational technology opens a qualitatively new stage in the development of the teaching methodology of subjects. At this stage, psychology is already of vital importance to him. According to scientific forecasts, in the near future, the methodology of teaching subjects will become essentially psychological, relying on the successes of psychology,

it will systematically approach the technology of teaching, along with the teaching situation (teaching tasks), the formation of teaching operations, control (self-monitoring) and assessment (self-evaluation) methodology issues will be clarified in detail. It seems that this will be the most important step in the way of optimizing the training process. [1; 154]

The result. 1) Referring to the research conducted on scientific sources, it was determined that there is a diversity of opinions regarding the interpretation of the concepts of "training" and "training process"; 2) It was determined that the concepts of "training", "training process", "educational activity of students" in educational psychology, the success achieved in the field of the formation of new pedagogical thinking and the concept of activity, led to the emergence of the concept of "educational activity"; 3) "Interpretation of the concept of "activities of students" in the educational process" was given by choosing the components of the structure of educational activities as a point of view based on the concept of educational activity.

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